

RAUWOLFININE: A NEW ALKALOID OF *RAUWOLFIA SERPENTINA*
BENTH. PART IV. STUDIES ON THE CONSTITUTION OF
RAUWOLFININE

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The partial structure of rauwolfinine, an indoline alkaloid (m.p. 235-36°), as reported previously, has been fully worked out and the entire structure of the base ($C_{19}H_{24}O_2N_2$) finally settled.

Rauwolfinine, an indoline alkaloid, m.p. 235-36°, occurring in *Rauwolfia serpentina* Benth. (of Dehra Dun variety) was shown to have the following partial structure (I) (Bose, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 47, 311, 691):

Further work on the constitution of rauwolfinine has been pursued and the entire structure of the base has been settled. The relevant informations are reported in the present communication.

The base, molecular formula $C_{19}H_{24}O_2N_2$ (I) of which has now been revised as $C_{19}H_{24}O_2N_2$ (Ia), does not undergo hydrogenation in presence of palladium-charcoal or Adams' catalyst and fails to react with lithium aluminium hydride. This observation implies that rauwolfinine is neither a dihydro- nor a tetrahydro- β -carboline derivative, which is in conformity with the colour reactions of the base. Obviously it is concluded that rauwolfinine is a hexahydro- β -carboline alkaloid (Ia). Acetyl, tosyl, chloro and benzoyl derivatives of the alkaloid cannot be prepared in a crystalline state. The products are always gummy, but they are found to be tetrahydro- β -carboline derivatives, as evidenced from their U.V. spectra and colour reactions

Several exploratory experiments, viz., alkali fusion, selenium dehydrogenation and dehydration etc., have been performed with a view to determining the nature of C_6H_5 (according to the new mol. formula) residue (Ia). From alkali fusion products (Bose, *loc. cit.*, p. 691) *n*-butyric, and no aromatic acid, has been isolated. The former has been characterised as its *p*-phenylphenacyl ester, m.p. 82-83°.

Selenium dehydrogenation of the base at 300° gives rise to several indoleaceous products from which Ind-*N*-methylharman, m.p. 101-102°, is obtained as a major product. The same experiment, performed at 250°, yields a different base, $C_{14}H_{18}N_2$, characterisation of which has not been possible for the paucity of materials.

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From the evidences accumulated so far, that rauwolfine is (i) a hexahydro- β -carboline derivative, (ii) produces *n* butyric acid and no aromatic acid upon alkali fusion, (iii) yields only Ind-*N*-methylharman but no yobyrine, alstyrine, or its lower homologues and their derivatives during selenium dehydrogenation, and considering the fact that all Rauwolfia alkaloids are tetracyclic, it can be assessed that rauwolfine bears a structural analogy with ajmaline (Woodward, *Angew. Chem.*, 1956, 68, 13). These facts together with the association of rauwolfine with ajmaline in Rauwolfia plants point out that the progenitor of these alkaloids is the same, which is shown in structure (II). Assuming Woodward's theory on the biogenesis of Rauwolfia alkaloids, as also the hypothesis on the biochemical oxidation of indole compounds developed by Witkop and Goodwin (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 3371), structural evolution of rauwolfine from (II) has been possible, as shown below:

Thus, during the biosynthesis of rauwolfine acetal condensation occurs at C₇-C₁₇ instead of aldol, as observed in ajmaline. In ajmaline R is an ethyl, whereas in rauwolfine (VI) it must be a methyl group as demanded by its molecular formula. Confirmation regarding the correctness of this structure (VI) follows from its behaviour towards 4N-H₂SO₄. When warmed with this reagent, the base develops an indole chromophoric group and is converted into a tetrahydro-β-carboline compound (VII) (evidence being provided by its U.V. spectrum and colour reactions). The resulting product strongly reduces ammoniacal silver nitrate solution and forms a crystalline 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, C₂₃H₂₈N₄O₄ (which decomposes above 200° but does not melt), indicating that an aldehyde group has developed in the product. This is exactly what is demanded by (VI), thus establishing the validity of the structure which is further strengthened by the fact that the base readily develops a tetrahydro-β-carboline nucleus when heated with PCl₅ and Ac₂O and *p*-Tosyl chloride, etc.

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